

The Synthesis of Some 6-Iodo-S-Substituted-2-Mercapto-3-Aryl-4-Quinazolones

P. N. Bhargava and Girish Chandra Singh

With a view to examine the medicinal utility of S-substituted-thioquinazolones, several 6-iodo-S-substituted-2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones have been synthesized.

The quinazolone derivatives have been studied by Baker *et al.*¹, Bami and Dhatt² as antimalarials; Gujral, Saxena and Tiwari³ as hyponotic agents in rats. The synthesis and properties of a series of 2-alkylthio-3-phenyl-4-quinazolones are reported by Mc Carty *et al.*⁴ and Bhargava and Phulgan Ram⁵.

The starting compounds, 6-Iodo-2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones(I) are prepared by refluxing 5-Iodoanthranilic acid and arylisothiocyanate in ethanol. The alkylation of the sodium derivatives of these quinazolones was done in aqueous alcoholic solution by appropriate halogen compounds obtained from secondary amines and chloroacetyl chloride⁶ in an inert solvent like benzene.

These reactions take place as shown below:

1. Baker *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 164.
2. H. L. Bami and M. S. Dhatt, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **16B**, 558; 1959, **18C**, 256.
3. M. L. Gujral, P. N. Saxena and R. S. Tiwari, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1955, **43**, 637; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1956, **50**, 6662.
4. Mc Carty *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 964.
5. P. N. Bhargava and P. Ram., *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, (Japan), 1965, **38**, 342.
6. Hahn, *B. Loos*, 51, 1442; Jacobs, Heidelberg, *J. biol. Chem.*, **21**, 149.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Iodo-anthranilic acid—This was prepared according to the method described by Blatt⁷.

6-Iodo-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone: Equimolecular quantities of 5-Iodoanthranilic acid, and phenylisothiocyanate were refluxed in sufficient ethanol on a water bath for 4—5 hours. The product was filtered, washed with a little ethanol, dissolved in moderate sodium hydroxide solution, precipitated by adding dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered by suction filtration, and crystallized from a mixture of chlorobenzene and ethanol (2:1), m.p. 295° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.32; S, 8.49. $C_{14}H_9N_2OSI$ requires: N, 7.37; S, 8.42%).

Similarly, other 6-Iodo-2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones were synthesized using 5-Iodoanthranilic acid and appropriate aryl isothiocyanates. The results and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

6-Iodo-2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones

No.	Aryl group	M.P. °C (decom- poses above)	Molecular formula	N, %		S, %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl-	295	$C_{14}H_9N_2OSI$	7.32	7.37	8.49	8.42
2.	o-Methylphenyl-	300	$C_{15}H_{11}N_2OSI$	7.01	7.11	8.01	8.12
3.	m-Methylphenyl—	303	$C_{15}H_{11}N_2OSI$	7.04	7.11	8.20	8.12
4.	p-Methylphenyl—	296	$C_{15}H_{11}N_2OSI$	7.00	7.11	8.16	8.12
5.	p-Chlorophenyl—	308	$C_{14}H_8N_2OSICl$	6.59	6.76	7.61	7.72
6.	p-Bromophenyl—	310	$C_{14}H_8N_2OSIBr$	6.02	6.10	6.80	6.97
7.	p-Methoxyphenyl—	299	$C_{15}H_{11}N_2O_2SI$	6.71	6.83	7.68	7.80
8.	p-Ethoxyphenyl—	294	$C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_2SI$	6.58	6.60	7.47	7.55

TABLE II

6-Iodo-2-diethylaminoacetylthio-3-aryl-4-quinazolones

No.	Aryl group	M.P. C	Molecular formula	N, %		S, %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl—	212	$C_{20}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$	8.48	8.52	6.38	6.49
2.	p-Methylphenyl—	184	$C_{21}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	8.10	8.28	6.20	6.31
3.	m-Methylphenyl—	175	$C_{21}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	8.12	8.28	6.28	6.31
4.	p-Methylphenyl—	202	$C_{21}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	8.20	8.28	6.22	6.31
5.	p-Chlorophenyl—	232	$C_{20}H_{19}N_3SO_2ClI$	7.80	7.96	5.99	6.07
6.	p-Bromophenyl—	221	$C_{20}H_{19}N_3SO_2BrI$	7.23	7.34	5.40	5.59
7.	p-Methoxyphenyl—	189	$C_{21}H_{22}N_3SO_3I$	8.00	8.03	6.00	6.12
8.	p-Ethoxyphenyl—	160	$C_{22}H_{24}N_3SO_3I$	7.70	7.82	5.80	5.96

6-Iodo-2-diethylaminoacetylthio-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone: 6-Iodo-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-quinazolones (7.6 g) was dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was then filtered, and mixed with N, N-diethylchloroacetamide (3 g) prepared

from chloroacetylchloride and diethylamine in benzene. The resulting product thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and a little ethanol, and crystallised from 50% ethanol into colourless crystalline form, m.p. 212°. (Found: N, 8.48; S, 6.38. $C_{20}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$, requires N, 8.52; S, 6.49%).

Following the same procedure other 6-Iodo-S-substituted-2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones have been prepared. The results are recorded in Table II, III, IV, V and VI.

TABLE III

6-Iodo-2-piperidinoacetylthio-3-aryl-4-quinazolones

No.	Aryl group	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	N, %		S, %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl—	203	$C_{21}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$	8.24	8.32	6.29	6.34
2.	o-Methylphenyl—	173	$C_{22}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	8.00	8.09	6.01	6.17
3.	m-Methylphenyl—	196	$C_{22}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	7.95	8.09	6.09	6.17
4.	p-Methylphenyl—	189	$C_{21}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	7.99	8.09	6.07	6.17
5.	p-Chlorophenyl—	194	$C_{21}H_{19}N_3SO_2ClI$	7.59	7.78	5.80	5.93
6.	p-Bromophenyl—	204	$C_{21}H_{19}N_3SO_2BrI$	7.00	7.19	5.38	5.48
7.	p-Methoxyphenyl—	184	$C_{22}H_{22}N_3SO_3I$	7.69	7.85	5.87	5.98
8.	p-Ethoxyphenyl—	157.5	$C_{23}H_{24}N_3SO_3I$	7.52	7.65	5.70	5.83

TABLE IV

6-Iodo-2-ethylphenylaminoacetylthio-3-aryl-4-quinazolones

No.	Aryl group	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	N, %		S, %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl—	200	$C_{24}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$	7.66	7.76	5.82	5.91
2.	o-Methylphenyl—	192	$C_{25}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	7.50	7.57	5.62	5.77
3.	m-Methylphenyl—	230	$C_{25}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	7.48	7.57	5.68	5.77
4.	p-Methylphenyl—	205	$C_{25}H_{22}N_3SO_2I$	7.51	7.57	5.65	5.77
5.	p-Chlorophenyl—	212	$C_{24}H_{19}N_3SO_2ClI$	7.21	7.30	5.49	5.56
6.	p-Bromophenyl—	204	$C_{24}H_{19}N_3SO_2BrI$	6.69	6.77	5.09	5.16
7.	p-Methoxyphenyl—	195	$C_{25}H_{22}N_3SO_3I$	7.20	7.36	5.54	5.60
8.	p-Ethoxyphenyl—	190	$C_{26}H_{24}N_3SO_3I$	7.09	7.18	5.38	5.47

TABLE V

6-Iodo-2-methylphenylaminoacetylthio-3-aryl-4-quinazolones

No.	Aryl group	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	N, %		S, %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl—	203	$C_{23}H_{18}N_3SO_2I$	7.83	7.97	5.98	6.07
2.	o-Methylphenyl—	206	$C_{24}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$	7.59	7.76	5.80	5.914
3.	m-Methylphenyl—	223	$C_{24}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$	7.69	7.76	5.82	5.914
4.	p-Methylphenyl—	195	$C_{24}H_{20}N_3SO_2I$	7.68	7.76	5.90	5.914
5.	p-Chlorophenyl—	185	$C_{23}H_{17}N_3SO_2ClI$	7.39	7.48	5.61	5.70
6.	p-Bromophenyl—	194	$C_{23}H_{17}N_3SO_2BrI$	6.76	6.93	5.10	5.28
7.	p-Methoxyphenyl—	208	$C_{24}H_{20}N_3SO_3I$	7.50	7.54	5.64	5.74
8.	p-Ethoxyphenyl—	180	$C_{25}H_{22}N_3SO_3I$	7.25	7.36	5.60	5.60

TABLE VI

6-Iodo-2-benzylphenylaminoacetylthio-3-aryl-4-quinazolones

No.	Aryl group	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	N, %		S, %	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Phenyl—	199	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₃ SO ₂ I	6.84	6.96	5.24	5.31
2.	o-Methylphenyl—	193	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₃ SO ₂ I	6.72	6.81	5.10	5.19
3.	m-Methylphenyl—	207	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₃ SO ₂ I	6.74	6.81	5.08	5.19
4.	p-Methylphenyl—	225	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₃ SO ₂ I	6.70	6.81	5.13	5.19
5.	p-Chlorophenyl—	194	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ SO ₂ ClI	6.48	6.59	5.00	5.02
6.	p-Bromophenyl—	200	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ SO ₂ BrI	6.11	6.16	4.57	4.69
7.	p-Methoxyphenyl—	226	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₃ SO ₃ I	6.64	6.63	5.01	5.06
8.	p-Ethoxyphenyl—	217	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₃ SO ₃ I	6.38	6.49	4.89	4.95

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5, INDIA.

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